

C-IMMSIM simulation results

August 16, 2025

Abstract

This document includes the plots relative to the simulation and the outcome of the epitope/peptide prediction used.

Produced by the C-IMMSIM Online server available at
<http://c-immsim.iac.rm.cnr.it> (alias to <http://kraken.iac.rm.cnr.it/C-IMMSIM>)

CITATIONS: For publication of results, please cite the following:

Nicolas Rapin, Ole Lund, Massimo Bernaschi, Filippo Castiglione. Computational Immunology Meets Bioinformatics: The Use of Prediction Tools for Molecular Binding in the Simulation of the Immune System. PLoS ONE 5(4): e9862
doi:10.1371/journal.pone.0009862, 2010

A retrospective validation

In-silico evaluation of adenoviral COVID-19 vaccination protocols: Assessment of immunological memory up to 6 months after the third dose. P. Stolfi, F. Castiglione, E. Mastrostefano, I. Di Biase, S. Di Biase, G. Palmieri, A. Prisco. Frontiers in Immunology, 13 (2022) doi: 10.3389/fimmu.2022.998262
<https://www.frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/fimmu.2022.998262>

An in vivo validation

Identification and validation of viral antigens sharing sequence and structural homology with tumor associated antigens (TAAs). C. Ragone, C. Manolio, B. Cavalluzzo, A. Petrizzo, A. Mauriello, M-L. Tornesello, F. M. Buonaguro, F. Castiglione, L. Vitagliano, M. Ruvo, M. Tagliamonte, L. Buonaguro. Journal for ImmunoTherapy of Cancer. 9:e002694 (2021)
<https://jitc.bmj.com/content/9/5/e002694>

Original C-IMMSIM model: www.iac.cnr.it/~filippo/c-immsim

GETTING HELP:

Scientific problems: Filippo Castiglione (filippo dot castiglione at cnr dot it)

Technical problems: Ilaria Gonnella (ilaria dot gonnella at cnr dot it)

Figure 1: Cell counts shown. Legend: Act=active, Intern=internalized the Ag, Pres II = presenting on MHC II, Dup = in the mitotic cycle, Anergic = anergic, Resting = not active.

Figure 2: Legend: symbols as figure above.

Figure 3: The virus, the immunoglobulins and the immunocomplexes.

Figure 4: Concentration of cytokines and interleukins. Inset plot shows danger signal together with leukocyte growth factor IL-2.

1] pos= -1 score=0.992206 unnormalised=104.841000000 non-binding event

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Allele: A0101
Pseudo sequence: KAVHAEQRNKAQTRA
Threshold: 9.456400
Max score: 29.236000

Antigen sequence file: /opt/lampp/htdocs/C-IMMSIM/Jobs/input/4946_20250816-125848_5_u42Eoc6RzWpw.FSA_1_001

FNCLGMSNRDFLEGVSGATVVDLVLEGDSCVTIMSKDKPTIDVKMMNMEANLAEVRSYCYLATVSDLSTKAACPTMGEA
HNDKRADPAFVCRQGVVDRGWNGCGLFGKGSIDTCAKFACTKAIGRTILKENIKYEVAIFVHGPTTVESHGNYSTQVG
ATQAGRFSITPAAPSYTLKLGEGYGEVTVDCPEPSGIDTNAYYVMTVGTKTFVHREWFMDLNLWPSSAGSTVWRNRETLM
EFEEPHATKQSVIALGSEQEGALHQALAGAIPEFSSNTVKLTSGHLKCRVKMEKLQLKGTTYGVCSKAFKFLGTPADTGH
GTVVLELQYTGTDGPKVPISSVASLNDLTPVGRLVTNPFVSVATANAKVLIELEPPFGDSYIVVGRGEQQINHHWHKS
G

Epitopes of protein 0 -----
0] pos= 146 score=0.007794 unnormalised=0.823600000 TTVESHGNY
1] pos= -1 score=0.992206 unnormalised=104.841000000 non-binding event

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Allele: B0702
Pseudo sequence: KAAREEQQIKAQTRE
Threshold: 8.702800
Max score: 28.406000

Antigen sequence file: /opt/lampp/htdocs/C-IMMSIM/Jobs/input/4946_20250816-125848_5_u42Eoc6RzWpw.FSA_1_001

FNCLGMSNRDFLEGVSGATVVDLVLEGDSCVTIMSKDKPTIDVKMMNMEANLAEVRSYCYLATVSDLSTKAACPTMGEA
HNDKRADPAFVCRQGVVDRGWNGCGLFGKGSIDTCAKFACTKAIGRTILKENIKYEVAIFVHGPTTVESHGNYSTQVG
ATQAGRFSITPAAPSYTLKLGEGYGEVTVDCPEPSGIDTNAYYVMTVGTKTFVHREWFMDLNLWPSSAGSTVWRNRETLM
EFEEPHATKQSVIALGSEQEGALHQALAGAIPEFSSNTVKLTSGHLKCRVKMEKLQLKGTTYGVCSKAFKFLGTPADTGH
GTVVLELQYTGTDGPKVPISSVASLNDLTPVGRLVTNPFVSVATANAKVLIELEPPFGDSYIVVGRGEQQINHHWHKS
G

Epitopes of protein 0 -----
0] pos= 169 score=0.062814 unnormalised=7.871200000 TPAAPSYTL
1] pos= 222 score=0.036311 unnormalised=4.550200000 LPWSSAGST
2] pos= 243 score=0.012794 unnormalised=1.603200000 EPHATKQSV
3] pos= 337 score=0.040661 unnormalised=5.095200000 VPISSVASL
4] pos= 349 score=0.005253 unnormalised=0.658200000 TPVGRLVTV
5] pos= 358 score=0.005516 unnormalised=0.691200000 NPFVSVATA
6] pos= -1 score=0.836652 unnormalised=104.841000000 non-binding event

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Threshold: 8.702800
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FNCLGMSNRDFLEGVSGATWVDLVLEGDSCVTIMSKDKPTIDVKMMNMEANLAEVRSYCYLATVSDLSTKAACPTMGEA
HNDKRADPAFVCRQGVVDRGWGNGCGLFGKGSIDTCAKFACSTKAIGRTILKENIKYEVAIFVHGPTTVESHGNYSTQVG
ATQAGRFSITPAAPSYTLKLGEGYEVTVDCPRSGIDTNAYYVMTVGTKTFLVHREWFMDLNLWPSSAGSTVWRNREITLM
EFEEPHATKQSVIALGSGEQALHQAALAGAIPEVFSSTVVKLTSGHLKCRVKMEKQLKLGTTYGVCSKAFKFLGTPADTGH
GTVVLELQYTGTDGPKVPISSVASLNDLTPVGRLVTNPFVSVATANAKVLIELEPPFGDSYIVVGRGEQQINHHWHKS
G

Epitopes of protein 0 -----

0]	pos= 169	score=0.062814	unnormalised=7.8712000000	TPAAPSYTL
1]	pos= 222	score=0.036311	unnormalised=4.5502000000	LPWSSAGST
2]	pos= 243	score=0.012794	unnormalised=1.6032000000	EPHATKQSV
3]	pos= 337	score=0.040661	unnormalised=5.0952000000	VPISSVASL
4]	pos= 349	score=0.005253	unnormalised=0.6582000000	TPVGRLVTV
5]	pos= 358	score=0.005516	unnormalised=0.6912000000	NPFVSVATA
6]	pos= -1	score=0.836652	unnormalised=104.8410000000	non-binding event

DoPeptideList_II:

Given the antigen injected creates the list of peptides for all the
NumAgProts proteins and for all i.e., 2 MHCII molecules

Read class II peptide list from file? NO

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Allele: DRB1_0101
Pseudo sequence: KFAHVEQRKAQTRV
Threshold: 2.392440
Max score: 26.461000

Antigen sequence file: /opt/lampp/htdocs/C-IMMSIM/Jobs/input/4946_20250816-125848_5_u42Eoc6RzWpw.FSA_1_001

FNCLGMSNRDFLEGVSGATWVDLVLEGDSCVTIMSKDKPTIDVKMMNMEANLAEVRSYCYLATVSDLSTKAACPTMGEA
HNDKRADPAFVCRQGVVDRGWGNGCGLFGKGSIDTCAKFACSTKAIGRTILKENIKYEVAIFVHGPTTVESHGNYSTQVG
ATQAGRFSITPAAPSYTLKLGEGYEVTVDCPRSGIDTNAYYVMTVGTKTFLVHREWFMDLNLWPSSAGSTVWRNREITLM
EFEEPHATKQSVIALGSGEQALHQAALAGAIPEVFSSTVVKLTSGHLKCRVKMEKQLKLGTTYGVCSKAFKFLGTPADTGH
GTVVLELQYTGTDGPKVPISSVASLNDLTPVGRLVTNPFVSVATANAKVLIELEPPFGDSYIVVGRGEQQINHHWHKS
G

Epitopes of protein 0 -----

0]	pos= 10	score=0.002814	unnormalised=0.4075600000	FLEGVSGAT
1]	pos= 42	score=0.017754	unnormalised=2.5715600000	VKMMNMEAA
2]	pos= 44	score=0.059019	unnormalised=8.5485600000	MMNMEANLA
3]	pos= 45	score=0.063879	unnormalised=9.2525600000	MNMEANLA
4]	pos= 58	score=0.010505	unnormalised=1.5215600000	YCYLATVSD
5]	pos= 60	score=0.035753	unnormalised=5.1785600000	YLATVSDLS
6]	pos= 134	score=0.015945	unnormalised=2.3095600000	IKYEVAIFV
7]	pos= 148	score=0.007729	unnormalised=1.1195600000	VESHGNYST
8]	pos= 154	score=0.018265	unnormalised=2.6455600000	YSTQVGATQ
9]	pos= 166	score=0.071460	unnormalised=10.3505600000	FSITPAAPS
10]	pos= 168	score=0.038880	unnormalised=5.6315600000	ITPAAPSYT
11]	pos= 201	score=0.046509	unnormalised=6.7365600000	YVMTVGTKT
12]	pos= 218	score=0.005030	unnormalised=0.7285600000	MDLNLWPSS
13]	pos= 239	score=0.009939	unnormalised=1.4395600000	MEFEEPHAT
14]	pos= 251	score=0.010905	unnormalised=1.5795600000	VIALGSGEQ
15]	pos= 261	score=0.047413	unnormalised=6.8675600000	LHQAALAGAI
16]	pos= 273	score=0.002041	unnormalised=0.2955600000	FSSNTVKLT
17]	pos= 310	score=0.018769	unnormalised=2.7185600000	FLGTPADTG

18]	pos= 354	score=0.008523	unnormalised=1.2345600000	LVTVNPVFS
19]	pos= 360	score=0.052046	unnormalised=7.5385600000	FVSVATANA
20]	pos= -1	score=0.456822	unnormalised=66.1680000000	non-binding event

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Allele: DRB1_0101
Pseudo sequence: KAFHVEQRKAQTRV
Threshold: 2.392440
Max score: 26.461000

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FNCLGMSNRDFLEGVSGATWVDLVLEGDSVCTIMSKDKPTIDVKMMNMEANLAEVRSYCYLATVSDLSTKAACPTMGEA
HNDKRADPAFVCRQGVVDRGWGNGCGLFGKGSIDTCAKACSTKAIGRTILKENIKYEVAIFVHGPTTVESHGNYSTQVG
ATQAGRFSITPAAPSYTLKLEGEYEVTVDCPEPRSGIDTNAYYVMTVGTKTFLVHREWFMDLNLPWSSAGSTVWRNREITLM
EFEEPHATKQSVIALGSEQEGALHQLAGAIPEVSSNTVKLTSGHLKCRVKMEKQLKGTTYGVCSKAFKFLGTPADTGH
GTVVLELQYTGTDGPKVPISSVASLNDLTPVGRLVTVNPVFSVATANAKVLELEPPFGDSYIVVGRGEQQINHHWHKS
G

Epitopes of protein 0 -----

0]	pos= 10	score=0.002814	unnormalised=0.4075600000	FLEGVSGAT
1]	pos= 42	score=0.017754	unnormalised=2.5715600000	VKMMNMEAA
2]	pos= 44	score=0.059019	unnormalised=8.5485600000	MMNMEANL
3]	pos= 45	score=0.063879	unnormalised=9.2525600000	MNMEANLA
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6]	pos= 134	score=0.015945	unnormalised=2.3095600000	IKYEVAIFV
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19]	pos= 360	score=0.052046	unnormalised=7.5385600000	FVSVATANA
20]	pos= -1	score=0.456822	unnormalised=66.1680000000	non-binding event